

MICROSTRUCTURE OF TITANIUM DIOXIDE (RUTILE)/ PURE ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The hardness of TiO₂/Al composites by squeeze casting is able to control easily by carrying out a heat treatment. The hardening of the composites is caused by Al₂O₃ and Al-Ti compounds reacted from TiO₂ and Al. For as-cast composites, TiO₂ particles are dispersed uniformly in Al matrix. On the other hand, the completely reacted composite is composed by the reaction products, and Al₂O₃ grains are dispersed uniformly. The interface between Al₂O₃ and Al-Ti compounds has a good coherent with little lattice mismatch. However, the crack propagate along Al₂O₃ and Al-Ti compound grains, so that the hardness of the composite seem to depend on the interface strength, strongly. In order to investigate the micromechanism that Na containing in TiO₂ particles decrease the temperature for TiO₂ and Al, Na was thermal doped to TiO₂ particles. Some structure changes are locally occurred on the surface of the particles, which seem to be a reaction site of TiO₂ and Al.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, titanium dioxide, aluminum, squeeze casting, reaction hardening, transmission electron microscopy, interface, sodium

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the study on the composites prepared by utilizing a reaction between aluminum alloys and inorganic reinforcements is watched with great interest because of the hardness, strength and some other mechanical properties of which are able to be controlled by carrying out a heat treatment after or during fabrication. Many remarkable fabrication techniques, such as Lanxide method[1], XD process[1], VLS process[2] and spontaneous infiltration technique[3] have been studied. Squeeze casting method have great advantage for the productivity and the workability. Authors fabricated TiO₂/Al alloy composites by squeeze casting, and found that the hardness of the composites is controlled easily by heat-treatment[4]. TiO₂ reacts slowly with solid Al resulting Al₂O₃ and Al-Ti compounds during heat-treatment process[5]. This composite is the mixture of metal matrix and intermetallic compound matrix composite, so that the hardness and strength of the composite are superior than the usual metal matrix composite. The composites fabricated by the reaction process are able to obtain the high performance compounds under the low temperature and easy forming condition. But the microstructure of the composite and the change of the micromechanism by the reaction are unknown.

Pure TiO₂ particles do not react with solid Al, so that the composites are not able to be hardened by heat treatment. It is also reported that alkaline metal and alkaline earth metal elements containing in the practical grade TiO₂ particles lead to decrease in the reaction temperature[6]. Especially, the elements having large ionic diameter such as Na assist the reaction of Al and TiO₂ with calorification above 873K. But the micromechanism about the effect of Na element containing in the particles is also unknown.

In order to improve the mechanical properties for TiO₂/Al composites, an analysis to the microstructure and micromechanism of the reaction is needed. This study puts stress on issues the structure change in the composite during the reaction and the effect of Na element on the reaction process.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

TiO₂ particles employed here were the rutile type with 0.3μm in diameter and its purity was 98.5% (practical grade, Wako Pure chemical Industry Ltd., Japan). In order to make clear the effect of Na element on the reactivity, the mixture of pure TiO₂ (99.9%, Wako Pure chemical Industry Ltd., Japan) and NaCO₃ powders was doped by ball milling (Pulverisette-5, Fritsch Ltd., Germany) and be heat-treated at 1373K for 3.6ks. Table 1 and Table 2 show the chemical compositions of practical grade TiO₂ particles and the impurity elements in high purity TiO₂ particles, respectively. In practical grade, 0.2 mass% NaO are contained. On the other hand, there is few Na content (7.8 mass ppm), and other alkaline and alkaline earth metal elements in high purity TiO₂ particles. The TiO₂ preform was fabricated by cold press forming with 0.3MPa and heat-treated at under 1373K for 1.8ks in atmosphere. The size of prepared preform is 30mm in diameter and 25mm in height and the volume fraction of TiO₂ is 40.5%. Pure Al (99.993%) was selected as the matrix and the composite was fabricated by a squeeze casting method at the molten metal temperature of 923K and preform temperature of 523K with the pressure of 100MPa. These parameters are almost the lowest temperature condition for the fabrication of a composite. Then the fabricated materials was heat-treated at a temperature between 773K and 1273K in atmosphere by the electric furnace. The microstructure and the reaction products were analyzed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD). TEM observation was carried out with JEOL/JEM4000EX for high resolution observation and JEOL/JEM2010 with EDS (NORAN/series II) for elemental analysis. SEM observation was carried out with HITACHI/S800.

Table 1. Chemical compositions of practical grade (85.5 mass%) TiO₂ particles.

(mass%)										
Al ₂ O ₃	ZnO	SiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	Na ₂ O	Nb ₂ O ₅	SO ₂	ZrO ₂	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂
2.71	1.03	0.56	0.19	0.2	0.15	0.08	0.047	0.01	0.005	bal.

Table 2. Impurity elements in high purity (99.9 mass%) TiO₂ particles.

(mass ppm)												
Al	Zn	Na	K	Ca	Fe	Ta	Cr	Ni	As	Pb	Mg	Ba
25.0	1.5	7.8	0.3	8.0	13.8	28.2	12.3	4.3	4.7	1.8	1.9	0.3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure of Practical Grade TiO₂ Particles/Al Composite

Figure 1 is some TEM photographs showing the microstructure of TiO₂/Al composites. The compounds of the composite were identified by EDS analysis. Fig. 1(a) shows the as-cast TiO₂/Al composites, which hardness is Hv 210. TiO₂ particles are dispersed uniformly in the Al matrix. Fig. 1(b) shows the composite heat-treated at 833K for 3.0ks, which hardness is Hv 400. Under this heat-treatment condition, the composite consists of TiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Al₃Ti compounds. But Ti₃Al compound was not observed. Al₂O₃ exists at the surface of TiO₂ particles and among Al₃Ti compounds. Fig. 1(c) is taken from the heat-treated composite at 973K for 0.3ks, which hardness is Hv 760. TiO₂ and Al were not observed under this condition. It seems that TiO₂ and Al in the composite react completely. The composites consist of Al₂O₃ and Al-Ti composites, such as Al₃Ti and Ti₃Al compounds. Al₂O₃ grains are dispersed uniformly in Al-Ti matrix and are equiaxed in shape with 10-50 nm in diameter. It seems that TiO₂ particles react with Al resulting in Al₂O₃ and Al₃Ti at first and then TiO₂ react with Al₃Ti forming Al₂O₃ and Ti₃Al.

Figure 2 is an enlargement of fig. 1(a) showing the microstructure of the as-cast TiO₂/Al composite. The black-white contrasts are observed in TiO₂ particles (fig. 2(a)). Fig. 2(b) shows the lattice arrangement of TiO₂ particles. Lattices have some curvature and disappeared here and there. The broad black-white contrast is due to strain field. It seems that the lattice of TiO₂ particles is distorted by the high pressure of squeeze casting and the compression stress caused by the solidification of Al matrix. Fig. 2(c) shows the atomic arrangement of the interface between TiO₂

Figure 1. TEM images of TiO₂/Al composites. (a) As cast, (b) 833K-3.0ks heat treatment, (c) 973K-0.3ks heat treatment.

Figure 2. TEM images of as-cast TiO_2/Al composites. (a) microstructure of the composite, (b) High resolution image inside TiO_2 particles, (c) high resolution image of the interface between TiO_2 particles and Al matrix.

and Al. The lattices of TiO_2 and Al connect directly. There is not any reaction product between TiO_2 and Al. The accurate interface position is not able to decide because of the good coherent. It seems that there is a epitaxial growth of Al on TiO_2 particles during solidification after a squeeze casting. Figure 3 is a microstructure of heat-treated composite at 973K for 0.3ks.

Fig. (a) is a high resolution observation at the interface between Al_2O_3 grain and Al_3Ti compound. In the heat-treated TiO_2/Al composites, the interface between Al_2O_3 and Al-Ti compounds formed by the reaction of TiO_2 and Al has a good coherent with little lattice mismatch. Fig. (b) shows a crack propagation in the microstructure. The crack propagates almost straightly along Al_2O_3 and Al-Ti compound grains. It seem that the interface strengths between Al_2O_3 and Al-Ti compounds or between the Al-Ti compound themselves are weak. The hardness and strength of the composite depend on these interface strength, strongly.

Figure 3. TEM images of heat-treated TiO_2/Al composite at 973K for 0.3ks. (a) high resolution image of the interface between Al_2O_3 and Al_3Ti compound (b) conventional image of the crack propagation.

Effect of Na Element in TiO_2 Particles

Na element in practical grade TiO_2 particles leads to a decrease in the reaction temperature during a heat treatment after the fabrication of the composites. In order to investigate this effect, Na element was doped to TiO_2 particles by ball milling. Figure 4 show that the microstructure of no-treated high purity TiO_2 particles (fig. 4(a)) and Na doped TiO_2 particles (fig. 4(b)). There is no difference for the morphology between Na doped and no-doped TiO_2 particles. Both the particles in fig. 4(a) and (b) are equiaxed in shape with about 300nm in diameter and have a straight surface. Table 3 is a EDS analysis of Na doped TiO_2 particles at the center and edge of the particle. At the center, the detected element was only Ti and O and the atomic ratio of Ti:O is about 1:2, which is equal to the composition of TiO_2 . At the edge, 0.28 at% Na element are detected. The EDS result illustrates that Na distributes only at the surface of the particle.

Figure 4. TEM images of high purity TiO_2 particles. (a) no-treated particle (b) Na doped particles.

(analyzed area : $\phi 3\text{nm}$)

Region	element (at%)		
	Ti	Na	O
X: Center	39.58	0.00	60.42
Y: Edge	31.51	0.28	68.21

Table 3. EDS analysis of Na doped TiO_2 particles in region X and Y shown in fig. 4 (b). Analyzed areas are 3nm in diameter.
(analyzed area : $\phi 3\text{nm}$)

Figure 5 is some high resolution images showing the microstructure of the interface. Fig. 5 (a) is the case of no-treated TiO_2 particle. There is an amorphous layer at the surface which is the contamination, such as organic matter. The surface structure shown in fig. 5 (b) are observed here and there in Na doped TiO_2 particle. By thermal doping Na to TiO_2 particles, an amorphous layer on the surface disappeared, and new structure layer generated. This New layer is 1-2nm in depth. The structure of it seem to be the complex oxide formed by Na and Ti. Some structure changes are locally occurred on the surface of the particles.

Figure 5. High resolution TEM images of the surface structure of TiO_2 particle. (a) No-treated TiO_2 particle (b) Na doped TiO_2 particle.

Figure 6 shows the microstructure of TiO_2/Al composite operated by SEM. TiO_2 particles employed here are the high purity grade (99.9%) with $5\mu\text{m}$ in diameter. Fig. 6(a) shows the no doped and as cast composite. TiO_2 particles are dispersed uniformly and the reaction products have not been observed. Fig. 6(b) is the no-doped and heat-treated composite at 873K for 86.4ks. The reaction products are observed at the interface between TiO_2 and Al. The white layers at the interface is Al_2O_3 which is formed by the reaction of TiO_2 and Al. Fig. 6(c) is the Na doped and heat-treated composite under the condition of 873K for 86.4ks. The reaction products are observed as the fine precipitates in TiO_2 particles. The reaction occurs

inside the TiO_2 particles. This phenomenon quite differ from that of the no-doped composite. Some structure changes are locally occurred on the surface of the TiO_2 particle and these areas become a reaction site of TiO_2 . Consequently, the reaction temperature is decreased and Al_2O_3 can be seen to precipitate inside the TiO_2 particles.

Figure 6. SEM images of the microstructure of TiO_2/Al composites. (a) As cast high purity TiO_2 composite (b) high purity TiO_2/Al composite with the heat treated under the condition of 873K for 86.4ks (c) Na doped TiO_2/Al composite heat treated under the condition of 873K for 86.4ks.

CONCLUSION

TiO_2/Al composites were fabricated by a squeeze casting and the changes of microstructure in the composite during the heat-treatment process were investigated. The mechanism of the stimulatory reaction by thermal doping Na to TiO_2 was analyzed.

- 1) For the as-cast TiO_2/Al composite, TiO_2 particles are dispersed uniformly in the matrix. There is not any reaction product between TiO_2 and Al. The lattice of TiO_2 particles is distorted by the high pressure of squeeze casting.
- 2) For the heat-treated TiO_2/Al composites, TiO_2 particles react with Al resulting in Al_2O_3 and Al-Ti compounds. The interface between Al_2O_3 and Al-Ti compounds has a good coherent with little lattice mismatch.
- 3) By thermal doping Na to TiO_2 particles, some structure changes are locally occurred on the surface of the particles in depth of 1nm. By heat-treating TiO_2/Al composite, Al_2O_3 formed inside TiO_2 particles. The spotty areas seem to be a reaction site of TiO_2 and Al, and the reaction temperature is decreased.

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